

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effect of depth of flooding on weeds rowing in association with flooded rice

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Flooding of rice checks weed germination and growth, although much of the applied water is wasted. Planting methods also indirectly affect weed growth. Drilled rice generally suffers more from weeds than does transplanted rice, even with flooding.

A 1972–73 field experiment at

Table 1. Effect of depth of flooding on weed dry weight and weed number in transplanted rice on puddled soil.^a Pantnagar, India, 1972–73 wet season.

Depth of flooding	Weed dry wt (g/m ²)				Weeds (no./m ²)			
	1972		1973		1972		1973	
	35 DT	Harvest	35 DT	Harvest	35 DT	Harvest	35 DT	Harvest
15 cm – 1m	1100	558	1927	640	51	32	72	30
5 cm–field capacity	1155	675	2003	651	68	38	95	58
1 cm–field capacity	3856	1975	2030	1000	197	121	152	62
32 cm total water (50% of total water use)	3891	1921	2100	1052	183	115	288	193
Rainfed	3902	1951	2119	1060	216	127	328	209
CD at 5%	194	137	100	61	–	–	–	–
CV (%)	5	6	2	3	–	–	–	–

^aDT = days after transplanting.

Pantnagar studied the effect of depth of flooding and planting methods on weed growth.

In both years, dry weight and number of weeds decreased when flooding depth increased. Transplanting in puddled soil

suppressed weed growth more than did direct drilling in unpuddled soil (Tables 1 and 2). Submergence created an unfavorable environment for most weed species. ■

Table 2. Effect of water management on weed dry weight and weed number in rice drilled on unpuddled soil.^a Pantnagar, India, 1972–73 wet season.

Water management treatment up to		Weed dry wt (g/m ²)				Weeds (no./m ²)			
21 DSE	21 DSE to maturity	1972		1973		1972		1973	
		45 DS	Harvest	45 DS	Harvest	45 DS	Harvest	45 DS	Harvest
1 cm – FC	15 cm – 1 cm	3640a	750e	3820a	620f	258	48	384	56
1 cm – FC	5 cm – FC	3380b	990c	3650b	1070c	234	68	307	130
1 cm – FC	1 cm – FC	3280c	1290a	3420c	1233b	203	52	208	156
5 cm – 1 cm	15 cm – 1 cm	2100g	840d	2225h	870d	150	58	124	78
5 cm – 1 cm	5 cm – FC	2400f	700e	2860e	790de	202	52	104	71
5 cm – 1 cm	1 cm – FC	2500f	1140b	2557g	998c	124	68	104	79
5 cm – FC	15 cm – 1 cm	2680e	550f	1710f	718f	182	36	120	64
5 cm – FC	5 cm – FC	2160g	840d	2290h	1081g	126	56	128	117
5 cm – FC	1 cm – FC	2970d	1302a	2995d	1357a	170	80	222	170

^aDSE = days after seedling establishment. DS = days after sowing. FC = field capacity. Any 2 means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly.

Soil and crop management

Fungi attack azolla in Bangladesh

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Of the six species of Azolla, *A. pinnata* is predominant in Bangladesh. The nitrogen that this aquatic fern supplies

to rice plants comes from activity of the blue-green algae *Anabaena*, which lives symbiotically within the fern leaves. Therefore, attempts are being made to mass-cultivate the plant under controlled and field conditions.

Azolla growth throughout the year is not constant mainly because of temperature and humidity variations.

Another factor that limits Azolla growth in Bangladesh is fungi attack. Two types of fungi were found to attack the fern leaves in multiplication tanks and pots during two different times of the year at BRRI. One such attack was in February–March and the other, in July–August 1979. During February–March azolla leaves blighted as the water in the tank